

Research Article

A new name for *Odontoglossum* × *luerorum* in the genus *Oncidium* (Orchidaceae)

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Abstract: The species epithet '*luerorum*' is preoccupied in the genus *Oncidium*, therefore, a new name *Oncidium* × *higginsii* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed here for *Odontoglossum* × *luerorum* Dalström & W.E.Higgins.

Keywords: Endemic, Ecuador, *Oncidium* × *luerorum*

Introduction

The genus *Oncidium* Sw. consists of about 380 species (including 38 hybrids), distributed in tropical and subtropical America (POWO, 2025; Singh & Kumar, 2025). In Ecuador, the genus is represented by about 106 species (including 6 hybrids), of which *O.* × *andreetteanum* (Dalström & G.Merino) J.M.H.Shaw, *O.* × *bockemuhliae* J.M.H.Shaw, *O. brevicorne* (Königer & J.Portilla) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. bustosii* Königer, *O. cristatellum* Garay, *O. deburghgraeveanum* (Dalström & G.Merino) J.M.H.Shaw, *O. echinops* Königer, *O. estradae* Dodson, *O. fleckiorum* Königer, *O. furcatum* (Dalström) J.M.H.Shaw, *O. gayi* J.M.H.Shaw, *O. gentryi* (Dodson) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. heterodactylum* Kraenzl., *O.* × *hinnus* (Rchb.f.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. hirtziana* J.M.H.Shaw, *O. hirtzoides* M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. lepidum* Linden & Rchb.f., *O.* × *lueroroides* M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O.* × *luerorum* (Dalström & W.E.Higgins) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *O. manningianum* Königer, *O. mantense* Dodson & R.Estrada, *O. marinii* (Königer) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. oxyceras* (Königer & J.G.Weinm.bis) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. peltiforme* Königer, *O. pichinchense* (Dodson) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. pongratzianum* Königer & J.Portilla, *O. portillae*

Königer, *O. portillaellum* M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. portilloides* M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams, *O. × strobiliorum* (Dalström & Deburghgr.) J.M.H.Shaw, *O. trinasutum* Kraenzl., *O. uncinatum* (Pupulin, G.Merino & J.Valle) J.M.H.Shaw, *O. universitas-cuencae* Königer & D.Vázquez, *O. universitas-lodziense* (Kolan., S.Nowak & Szlach.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *O. weinmannianum* (Königer) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams are endemic (POWO, 2025). In current circumscription, *Odontoglossum* Kunth is included under the synonymy of the genus *Oncidium* (Chase et al., 2015). Recently, a new combination was made for *Odontoglossum × luerorum* Dalström & W.E.Higgins under the genus *Oncidium* as *O. × luerorum* (Dalström & W.E.Higgins) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar (2025: 105). However, the name *O. × luerorum* (Dalström & W.E.Higgins) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is illegitimate, because it is a later homonym of *O. luerorum* Dodson (Orquideologia 20: 91. 1996). Therefore, a new name *O. × higginsii* R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed here for *Odontoglossum × luerorum*.

Nomenclature

Oncidium × higginsii R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Odontoglossum × luerorum* Dalström & W.E.Higgins, Lankesteriana 19(1): 17. 2019. *Oncidium × luerorum* (Dalström & W.E.Higgins) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(1): 105. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Dodson, Orquideologia 20: 91. 1996.

Holotype: Ecuador, Carchi, epiphytic in cloud forest above Maldonado west of Tulcan, 2000–2500 m, 25 August 1978, C. Luer, J. Luer & A. Hirtz 3373 (SEL).

Distribution: Endemic to Ecuador.

Etymology: Named after Wesley Ervin Higgins, American Botanist and Orchidologist.

Hybrid parents: *Oncidium armatum* (Rchb.f.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams [≡ *Odontoglossum armatum* Rchb.f.] × *Oncidium mirandum* (Rchb.f.) M.W.Chase & N.H.Williams [≡ *Odontoglossum mirandum* Rchb.f.].

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